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MALPRACTICES IN FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

Malpractices in the banking industry are not only contrary to the ethics of the banking profession, but also constitute infringements of various banking laws and regulations. The objective of this paper is to identify the major malpractices in the banking industry and recommend measures to address them. The scope of this paper however will not include other banking infractions or unethical practices whereby banks make huge illegal profits from customers' monies, through decimalization of the customers' monies. The sources of information relied upon in this research include relevant books, articles in journal publications, conference materials, internet, case laws and statutes. The research findings revealed that, malpractices and other related crimes have significant effect on the financial institutions in Nigeria. It was also clear that fraudulent activities in the banking sector are carried out with the aid and support of banking officials. The banks usually fire or dismiss employees for misconduct and malpractice whenever their activities are discovered. It is therefore recommended that officials of the banking sector should willingly co-operate with the police in the early report of fraud cases and immediate handing over of suspected bank officials to the police for a thorough investigation before their dismissals are communicated to them. Also Auditors and Accountants in organizations and financial institutions should be trained on how to carry out forensic investigation since the fraudsters are now sophisticated in their act. Finally, internal

control systems should be strengthened to block opportunities that attract fraud perpetrators and oversight function of the National Assembly be strengthened to make public office holders more accountable.

Keyword: Financial Institution, Malpractice, Banking Industry, Banks.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Malpractices in banks are those acts or omissions which are not only just contrary to the ethics of the banking profession, but also constitute infringements of various banking laws and regulations. These acts or omissions are sanctioned by banking practice, and is accepted by everyone else as wrongful practices and thus illegal. There are three broad categories of malpractices that will be addressed in this paper, namely: malpractices by bank employees, malpractices by non-employees of the banks and malpractices by the banks as independent institutions.

Firstly, Bank employees' malpractices are mainly malpractices perpetrated by bank employees against the interests of their banks or the banks customers, solely for their personal benefits (the employees), or for the joined benefits of themselves and their outside collaborators. Such malpractices include stealing of banks' and customers' monies, falsification of accounts and forgery of bank papers for the purposes of stealing or in order to corruptly enrich themselves, or deliberately breaching banking rules to make money etc.

Stealing by high ranking employees at the managerial level: This type of stealing maybe committed by cashiers from their daily cash receipts or committed by other employees who steal from monies in the custody of cashiers, who maybe momentarily absent from their cages without locking up. While in-managerial stealing maybe committed in so many ways, including stealing money from the strong room, to replacing strong-room money with forged currency notes. However, the most painful of these acts of theft is now done by fake and fraudulent transfers of bank funds from one bank to the other. Such fraudulent transfers are now considerably aided by the use of telexes and computers. This practice usually involves collusion by employees of, at least, two banks.

Stealing of Customers' Monies can be by a simple or complicated method. Instances of simple methods maybe where a customer pays money into the bank and the cashier counting the money drops some money into his till from a packet, and then claims that the packet is incomplete. The unsuspecting customer then begins to doubt his own calculation or counting, or the honesty of his staff or members of his family who assisted him in counting the money. The reverse situation may again occur in the case of withdrawal of

money by a regular customer who believes in the honesty and infallibility of bank staff or one who is in a hurry. Here, the cashier may pay a lesser amount of money to the customer. If the customer fails to count the money immediately on receipt of the money in the presence and in full view of the cashier, he himself will hardly come back to complain on the shortfall. Sometimes, the situation occurs in the course of payment of large sums to big customers, usually companies, government departments or parastatals, where some few packets may have minor shortfalls.

Secondly, malpractices by non-employees of the banks: Instances may range from fraudulent intra-bank crediting and debiting of customers' accounts, with a view to transferring money from one account to the other from which arrangements have been made to take the money out. The same may also be achieved through the passage of a forged cheque which, more often than not, usually involves collusion with non-banking officials, like the staff of the customer whose cheque is forged. The debiting and crediting, and the subsequent reversals, are simply explained off as machine or computer errors. Also, a fat account, which remains dormant for quite some time, is often the target for such exercises.

Thirdly, malpractices by non-employees of banks: as mentioned above, the malpractice of passing forged cheques to steal bank customers' monies is well known in the banking industry. So also is the malpractice of inducing fraudulent transfers of monies from customers' accounts with forged documents. At present, Nigerian banks are battling with the effect of fake international tested telexes purportedly sent by Nigerian banks to foreign banks, authorizing those banks to transfer certain amounts into certain accounts outside country. Such transfers will result in the Nigerian banks in question, or their customers, losing their monies to the international crooks.

The area which the Nigerian banks should focus on is the area of computer transfers. Our banks and law enforcement authorities at present do are not abreast of the incidence of computer frauds in practice. Through the use of the computer terminal at branches fraudulent transfers discussed are readily facilitated. It is now possible for a bank branch to log in into the computer central database of another branch (or even from one bank computer to another) and programme another branch's or bank to transfer money from its

account(s) into designated account(s) at the originating bank branch or elsewhere. Hence the banks need adequate training for their staff about building a lot of security checks into their computer systems and carefully guarding same. This will involve letting the general staff have access only to the routine of the packaging system; whilst the secret codes for the security checks/guards should be known only to the Managing Director and one or two of his top aides, or to the Computer Operations top cadre (not more than two or three in number). Such people must have and bear full responsibility for computer operations in their banks. They should, of course, periodically test their systems for security leakages; and change their codes where leakages have been discovered or suspected. It is essential and urgent for our banks to take serious precautions in this area, bearing in mind that computers now operate via satellite, so telecommunications transmission have demonstrated. The implication of this is that a very competent foreign resident computer scientist can induce transfer of funds from any of our banks via satellite at will, unless adequate care is taken. The prospects of this must be quite frightful for a developing country like Nigeria.

Malpractices by the banks such as exceeding credit ceilings. The Central Bank of Nigeria imposes a general credit ceiling on banks on the percentages of their operational funds which they may lend out as loans. Within these limits, it then sets out guidelines for the sectoral allocations of such loan funds. In this regard, it is known that banks breach the Central Bank of Nigeria's Guidelines on sectoral allocations. Such breaches maybe due to the quest for excessive profits, namely: operating policies which result in neglect of the less lucrative areas, whilst diverting their loan activities into lucrative areas even in excess of the sectoral ceilings imposed by the guidelines. Such activities are classified as malpractices.

The incidence of malpractice in the Nigerian financial institutions has become a matter of serious concern to all. It is against this background that this paper sets out to examine the menace and its effects on bank performance in Nigeria.

2.0 MALPRACTICES IN FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

i FALSIFICATION OF ACCOUNTS AND FORGERIES FOR STEALING PURPOSES AND CORRUPTION

The situations reported in the two subsections above offer ample illustrations of these malpractices, and they will, thereafter not be further elaborated upon here separately.

There are two broad categories of corruption among banking officials, namely: corruption involving falsification of accounts and other documents, and corruption involving breaches of banking rules. In either case, it is with a view to highly placed banking officials enriching themselves, their cronies, friends or some persons in position of authority.

Quite apart from falsifying accounts and other documents for purposes of stealing money from the banks or their customers, bank officials also use these methods for other fraudulent purposes. For example, in order to back up illegal transfer of foreign exchange, bank officials, in collusion with customs officials and the Nigerian Ports Authority officials, conspire with customers to prepare Letters of Credit for unimproved goods, or for an amount considerably more than (maybe ten times) the actual amount of goods actually ordered and imported into the country. All the banking documents, customs documents and the Nigerian Ports Authority documents are false or entirely fake. The Central Bank, whose officials may also be in collusion, will then authorize the foreign exchange transfers due on the imaginary imports supported by the fake or falsified papers. Strangely, shortly after the transfers, all the relevant documents often disappear from the banks, including those with the Central Bank, Customs Department and the Nigerian Ports Authority. No wonder it is difficult to know exactly how much of foreign debts we owe and specifically for what, even from the Central Bank of Nigeria.

Similarly, on the local scene, for good financial gratification, or some other consideration, documents relating to a loan can be made to disappear in transit from a bank headquarters to a branch in expectation of reward or promotion, respect for, or fear of, the political or administrative position of the debtor, or the relationship of the debtor to certain official(s). In the case of non-observance of rules, this relates largely to areas of loans. Here, for a particular percentage (share of the loan), the manager may decide to grant a loan exceeding his authority without reference to the appropriate headquarters for approval. Again, he may even grant the loan without any collateral. Instances abound of bank managers granting unlimited overdraft facilities to their wives, girl-friends, relations, friends without any collateral. Queries resulting in severe disciplinary actions, including

demotions and dismissals have been issued by the authorities of certain Nigerian banks for the malpractices outlined above. The Central Bank of Nigeria (as well as the Customs and the Nigerian Port Authority) is known to have taken disciplinary actions against its officials for corruption.¹

There is also the practice of bank managers clearing government and public parastatals' cheques contrary to rules against these and paying out monies on them before after normal clearance elapses. They sometimes give large credit on cheques before they are cleared. This latter practice is usually due to corrupt motivation, or the reputation of the customer.

However, when one examines certain areas in these guidelines, like investments in the manufacturing, mining, agricultural, and property investment sectors, one must consider the types of banks. By the nature of things, commercial banks deal only in short-term transactions, whilst the merchant banks deal in longer term transactions. The Central Bank of Nigeria must take into this into consideration when formulating guidelines global and sectoral.

It is, of course, realized that there is still much room for the growth of our banking industry both in the sizes and the diversification of their operations. In the recent past, we had too few merchant's banks that could adequately cater for the long-term investments required in the Nigerian economy. Hence, the imposition of the long-term investment activities on the commercial banks. But the situation is now fast changing, and many merchant banks have been springing up recently, thanks to the lucrative foreign exchange business for the banks! I believe that the time has now come for the Central Bank of Nigeria in its guidelines for the various sectors to realistically distinguish between the two types of banks, and pragmatically allocate only the short-term investment and some medium-term investment sectors to the commercial banks; whilst the remaining medium-term investment sectors and the long-term investment sectors should be allocated to the merchant banks. It will then be absolutely just and proper to review the penalties for infringements in such a way that the banks will find breaches both inconvenient and

¹ It is for the reason of checking such and other malpractices that the Bank Employees, etc. (Declaration of Assets) Decree, No. 24 of 1986, was promulgated.

unprofitable. Of course, full consultations should be held with the two groups of banks in such reformulation of the sectoral guidelines.

Also, it is necessary for the authorities to provide adequate cover for banks which are being asked to get involved in assisting the purchase of shares or property development. As long as the shares being bought cannot really be regarded as collateral securities for the loans advanced for the purchase of those shares the banks will hardly be expected to part with their money to shareholders whom they cannot compel to part with their shares in the event of default in repayment or total failure to pay back the loan. Since banks are not charitable institutions, it will be necessary for relevant reform to be effected in this regard before society can expect the banks to operate fully in this area.

The second problem here is that the returns on the shares investments in the form of dividends, will lag behind the interest rates for the loans advanced for their purchase. So, the customers are bound to lose. Consequently, as the bank customers become better educated in investment calculations, it must be realized that the banks will never “perform” well in this area, since members of the public will hardly want to borrow at an interest rate of 20%, and make a dividend profit of 4% - 7% on the shares purchased with the loans.

In the areas of agricultural and property development investments, the vagaries of title caused by the Land Use Act, 1978, particularly the power of revocation, must make any bank extraordinarily cautious in committing its money into those areas. The timidity of our courts in this regard has not helped matters at all.²

However, having said this much for the need to review the overall situation, the functioning of the banks themselves has left very much to be desired, as it is difficult to discern sometimes whether these Nigerian institutions really do consider that if they assist in the promotion of the growth of the national economy, they will in turn be assisting themselves to grow and develop, not only nationally, but also internationally. They must realize, therefore, that they have a real stake in the economy. It is for this reason that it must remain unpardonable for a bank to deliberately breach the guidelines designed, in principle, for the

² See *Nkwocha v. Governor of Anambra State* (1984) 6 S.c. 362; *LSFPC v. Foreign Finance Corporation* (1987) 2 NWLR (Pt. 50), 413; *Salami v. Oke* (1987) 4 NWLR (Pt. 63), 1; *Savannah Bank v. Ajilo* (1989) 1 NWLR; 28.

healthy inter-sectoral development of the economy, and to exhibit a preference to be more ready to pay the penalty for breaches than to observe the guidelines, simply because it stands to gain a lot financially from breaches when compared to the paltry losses through penalties. In this regard, I refer specifically to the attitude of the commercial banks to lending for distributive trade at the present stage of the development of the Nigerian economy. Their attitude of over-lending here is largely encouraging large-scale foreign goods importation, to the detriment of the growth of the local industries; and, worse still, the attitude has constituted an encouragement to the smuggling of foreign goods into the country. Such a brazen and patently 'damaging-to-the-economy' malpractice must be condemned. Perhaps is not realized that such a malpractice should qualify as economic sabotage under the Special Tribunal (Miscellaneous Offences) Law.

Similarly, the malpractice of brazenly exceeding the overall borrowing ceiling allowed by the Central Bank of Nigeria purely because of the gains the banks stand to make should similarly be regarded as economic sabotage. In both cases, the banks shouldn't escape conviction and punishment of the Tribunal for their actions only if it is for the overall good of the economy. Banks should no longer be treated as if they are above the law of the land by getting away with only petty fines. This must be particularly so because the banks have been so largely the veritable instruments by which considerable damage has been wrought on the Nigerian economy. Our large foreign debts have been largely due to the disreputable activities of our banks, which have co-operated in the large-scale fraud as regarded letters of credit, negotiation of false bills of exchange, processing of fraudulent foreign exchange transfers, et cetera.

ii ILLEGAL SALES OF FOREIGN EXCHANGE

Apart from fraudulent transfers of foreign exchange, just as discussed in the cases of bank officials and other non-banking personnel with the aid of forged documents, Nigerian banks have engaged in illegal sales of foreign exchange. The Foreign Exchange Market was further deregulated, and the 'Bureau de Change' was introduced. Although. Meanwhile, inter-bank dealings have been allowed; whilst the banks have also been allowed to make their own direct purchases of foreign exchange from independent but legitimate sources.

The first malpractice is that banks are known to be purchasing foreign exchange from independent sources in circumstances almost similar to what obtains in the 'parallel' or the 'black' market.³ The banks then sell off such privately purchased foreign exchange to their customers at exorbitant rates.

The second malpractice here is that the banks hoard their officially purchased foreign exchange. They are able to account for their sales by entering into their sales the transactions involving their sales of the parallel market purchases. This then involves cooking up the books to reflect what are considered to be acceptable exchange sales rates, which do not often reflect the actual rates of exchange sales. The hoarded officially acquired foreign exchange is also sold at exorbitant rates, leading to exorbitant overall profits all-round for the banks. Where any such malpractices have been discovered, the banks at fault have been suspended from bidding at the next auction.

The damaging effect of these malpractices has been that a lot of pressure has been and is being put on the naira, and this has been responsible for its considerable depreciation. Its further collapse has been prevented by the ready availability of foreign exchange in the market, due to the large-scale influx of foreign. If such monies had not been available, the naira would have suffered much greater depreciation by now.

Perhaps, it is high time we completely removed the lid and allowed free sale of foreign exchange outside the banks, licensed the 'Bristol Hotel' and 'Abibu Oki Street' merchants⁴, and removed from the banks the monopoly to sell foreign exchange. The results of these actions may be slow, their success will be sure, as they are bound to encourage much freer flow of foreign exchange into the country. The black or parallel market will disappear. The experiences of Egypt and Libya are there for us to benefit from. In the long run, Nigeria will stand to benefit from these steps, as Egypt has benefited. And, where the desirable investment climate is created, liberalization of foreign exchange transactions will aid a more rapid and more massive foreign investment flow into the country.

iii ROUND TRIPPING OF FUNDS

³ Definitely, this was not what was envisaged by the deregulation dispensation contained in the 1989 Budget Proposals.

⁴ Which is what the 'Bureau de Change' is supposed to achieve.

This is the practice whereby a foreign bank would guarantee a local loan for a local project. Usually, the foreign bank would be a corresponding bank or an affiliate of the local bank. The two banks would then enter into collusion and the following scenario would emerge: on the raising of the bank guarantee by the foreign bank to the Nigerian bank to back up an application to the Nigerian bank for a loan in *naira* for the execution of a project in Nigeria, the Nigerian bank would then decide to grant the loan. The project would subsequently be executed in Nigeria. All necessary foreign importations would be effected by the normal procedure of purchasing the required foreign exchange on the open foreign exchange market in Nigeria. Usually, during the execution or after the completion of the project, all the parties, namely the contractor or project proprietor, the Nigerian bank and the foreign bank would, in accordance with their initial conspiracy, record the failure to execute or complete the project. The Nigerian bank would then formally call upon the foreign bank to remit the amount of the foreign exchange provided for in its guarantee to enable the completion of the project or reimbursement of itself. The foreign exchange so transferred would then be sold at exorbitant rates locally. After the deduction of its own profit locally, the remaining amount would then be transmitted back to the foreign bank through the purchase of foreign exchange in the Nigerian market. All the parties to the conspiracy, banks and individuals concerned, would then share the remaining profit over and above the original sum guaranteed in foreign exchange.

The issue here is that the involvement of the foreign bank in the form of a guarantee usually does not result in any actual foreign investment in the country. Additionally, it operates to drain further our available scarce foreign and local resources. Consequently, this malpractice, in effect, operates to reduce the amount of foreign exchange available to the country for real investment for the development of the economy. Also, further depreciation of the naira at the time of the remittance of the money abroad would also result in the contraction of the amount of naira that would have been available for local investment in the Nigerian economy. Consequently, it was a welcome relief.⁵

⁵ See the Editorial of the *Daily Times*, Thursday, 20 April, 1989, for comments.

3.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Below are some literature reviews on the subject matter.

Olaoye C.O. and Dada R.A. in their article titled; Analysis of Frauds in Banks: Nigeria's Experience⁶, assessed the nature, causes, effects, detection and prevention measure for bank frauds in Nigeria. The authors further stressed that in spite of the fact that banking industry is the most controlled and regulated industry in Nigeria, fraud has continued to rear its ugly head in the industry. It has eaten deep into every units and department in the banking sector. The level of fraud in the present day Nigeria has assumed an epidemic dimension. Nigeria with all its human and natural resources, tethers on the brink of failure because of fraud. Much of what we do is "cutting leaves" instead of dealing with the root problem. The authors concluded that in the fight for the prevention of fraud, banks should have in place sound/effective internal control mechanism/checks and balances and provide adequate remuneration and reward for excellence and good conduct while the incessant and periodic downsizing of bank staffs should be discouraged. There should be steadfastness in punishing offenders and adoption of zero tolerance to corruption. The society should imbibe cultural value system of treating fraudsters with contempt. The study is centered on only one aspect (fraud) of malpractice in the financial institutions which gives room for improvement by discussing other aspects of malpractice.

According to Iloh A. U. and Adie a. N,⁷ in their article titled: The Impact of Financial Malpractices on the Productivity of the Public Sector in Nigeria, financial Malpractice may occur when a financial professional fails to make suitable financial report or records of actual transactions or trades as ordered by the financial regulations/rules guiding the operations of Public Financial Management. For instance, charging excessive fees or commits theft or fraud/embezzlement of funds, misappropriation of funds, etc., these may

⁶ Olaoye C.O. and Dada R.A. (2017) Analysis of Frauds in Banks: Nigeria's Experience. *European Journal of Business and Management*. Vol.6, No.31

⁷ Iloh, A. U., & Adie, A. N. (2019). THE IMPACT OF FINANCIAL MALPRACTICES ON THE PRODUCTIVITY OF THE PUBLIC SECTOR IN NIGERIA: A CASE STUDY OF FEDERAL INLAND REVENUE, ENUGU STATE. *African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 9(2). Retrieved from <https://journals.aphriapub.com/index.php/AJSBS/article/view/1690>. Vol. 9 No. 2. accessed 24/07/2023.

also be considered as financial malpractice in the public services. From their study, it is clear that financial malpractices exist in the public service and becoming a norm and that most stakeholders are perpetrators of it, also the control system is weak and it affects both the national economy and the output of workers. According to the authors, the government has strategies to control malpractices but it is inadequate. It was therefore, recommended that government should establish more strategies of control, monitoring and evaluations of accounting procedures and also ensures offenders are brought to book by the law. Finally, advanced technological equipment, like CCTIVs should be installed in public offices to monitor activities.

Okoye, E.I. and Gbegi, D.O in their article titled: An Evaluation of the Effect of Fraud and Related Financial Crimes on the Nigerian Economy⁸, try to determine the impact of fraud and related financial crimes on the growth and development of Nigerian economy. According to the authors, economic and financial crimes in whatever form and nature have potentially devastating impacts on economy, security and social wellbeing of the people. It is perhaps pertinent to stress that as modern financial system encourages and facilitates local and international commerce, antithetically, financial criminals are also enabled by modern financial global liberalization to transfer millions of dollars around the world instantly through available information communication infrastructures such as internet, electronic money transfer (wire transfer) and the rest. From the study, it was revealed that, fraud and related financial crime has significant effect on the Nigerian economy while fraud and financial crime have no significant effect on inflation. Based on the research findings, the authors recommended that Auditors and Accountants in organizations and financial institutions should be trained on how to carry out forensic investigation since the fraudsters are now sophisticated in their act. Also internal control systems should be strengthened to block opportunities that attract fraud perpetrators and oversight function of the National Assembly be strengthened to make public office holders accountable.

⁸ Okoye, E.I. and Gbegi, D.O (2013) An Evaluation of the Effect of Fraud and Related Financial Crimes on the Nigerian Economy. Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review Vol. 2, No.7.

4.0 METHODOLOGY

This research is based on doctrinal research methodology approach as opposed to the empirical study which concerns itself with practical and details. Doctrinal research is concerned with legal proposition and doctrines. It is research into the law and legal concepts. Therefore, the sources of data here include; legal and appellate court decisions, legal concepts and principles of all types, statutes, relevant books, articles in journal publication, conference papers and internet materials.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

- i. The study revealed that; financial malpractice exists in the financial institutions and it has become the order of the day as if it is a norm; the masses, bank workers and stakeholders are the perpetrators of financial malpractice in the financial institutions.
- ii. The research findings revealed that, malpractices and related crimes has significant effect on the financial institutions in Nigeria.
- iii. The study revealed that fraudulent activities in the banking sector are carried out with the aid and support of bank officials. The banks usually fire or dismiss employees for misconduct and malpractice whenever their activities are discovered.

6.0 CONCLUSION

This paper discussed many of the various malpractices perpetrated by bank officials, non-bank officials and the banks themselves. Many situations of collusion among the three categories of these malpractitioners have been instanced.

It was found that in relation to staff training and security in banks, there is the need to review inter-sectoral and overall lending ceiling(s) allocations to the banks, taking into consideration the real needs of the economy for rapid growth stimulation, and the pragmatic appreciation of the distinction between the commercial banks and the merchant banks. Also, there the need for a more comprehensive review of the economy was also stressed, with the specific need for a complete deregulation of the foreign exchange transactions and the creation of suitable climate for foreign investments.

However, once these liberalizations have been put in place, Nigeria must then re-order its priorities so as to attract foreign investments. It must decide on the areas in which foreign investments are required, and provide the necessary incentives which will attract foreign investments to such areas. The determination of such priority areas should be undertaken on periodic basis.

However, in view of the fact that the banking industry is the backbone of every national as well as international economy and in view of the various malpractices highlighted here, the deleterious effects of which I had previously highlighted in my earlier paper on "Economic Crime In A Developing Society",⁹ it should now be realized by everyone that large-scale stealing of bank funds or customers' funds, falsification of accounts and forgery of documents resulting in large-scale losses to banks, individuals and the country, harmful dealings in foreign exchange, corrupt practices resulting in serious bank, individual and national losses, and any other bank activities resulting in serious losses to the economy, whether in local or foreign currencies must henceforth be regarded as economic sabotage with the attendant legal consequences.

No serious country should continue to accept the contradiction of excessive profits in a depressed economy, which can only result from deliberate policy(ies) to refuse to engage in the maximum investment possible in any year. Such a policy or policies will always fail to give the maximum possible stimulation to our economy. In this regard, the banks are not alone. The trading and manufacturing companies are equally guilty. The latter even stubbornly refusing to exploit avenues which will reduce their dependency on foreign imports.¹⁰

One way out is to sharpen our taxation policy to encourage the banks and companies expand their investments and re-investments in the economy or face the alternative of losing a considerable portion of their profits to the government in taxation. No government,

⁹ *Ibid.*, *op. cit.*, at pp. 8, 9, 10-12, 13 and 15.

¹⁰ It will not be out of place to prosecute for economic sabotage manufacturing companies which deliberately try to obstruct the national movement to the development of local raw materials for their industry, like the present wheat fracas, or those which refuse to accept feasible local machineries developed for manufacturing their products here in Nigeria. Our technology will never grow unless we actually utilize the products of such technological efforts, in the way the Chinese utilized their local technological efforts; whilst the proclaimed objective of our Structural Adjustment Programme will never be realized unless that is done and local raw materials are utilized.

anywhere in the world, has ever been known to be in the habit of writing a "Thank You" letter to any taxpayer, however large the tax he paid.

The conclusion of the other efforts of the government currently in progress, in the areas of fighting corruption and other economic crimes, the reform of company law, and the unification and reform of the criminal laws and criminal procedures of Nigeria, will comprehensively aid the effective combating of banking and other financial malpractices. Lastly, it is now high time that the law protecting bankers who have not been shown to be negligent in any way in the course of their payment or transferring of money from a customer's account, on the basis of a forgery be changed. Unless it can be shown that that the customer is either in collusion or is negligent, there is no basis for the law to make him suffer when he is in no way involved in the transaction between the forger and the paying bank thereby making the bank liable for the loss arising from the payment rather than the customer will have the effect of increasing banking vigilance and astuteness just like what obtains in the insurance industry.

Besides, when we view the matter morally, as between the nonparticipating customer and the paying bank, it seems that if anybody should bear any fault it should be the paying bank. The present law making the customer bear the loss is, therefore, unjust, and should be changed to make the bankers who, in any event, have more resources to absorb the losses better than the poor customer liable for such losses.